

ESTIMATION OF CHLORINE IN ORGANIC COMBINATION IN THE COAL SUBSTANCE

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Modified ter Meulen method has been attempted in evaluating chlorine in coal substance in organic combination.

It is a matter of common experience that chlorine, in proportions varying between 0.05 and 1.0%, occurs in all coals. Many hold the view that this chlorine is present principally as chlorides of sodium, potassium and magnesium in the coal substance. There is, again, no suitable method for determining the water-soluble chlorine in coal and, as such, a measure of total chlorine is ordinarily found out (Fuel Research Board, Survey paper No. 44, 1940, p. 28). This is perhaps the reason why chlorine is considered to be present predominantly as chlorides. A correct measure of the chlorine, as chlorides, provides its effective usefulness in the case of coals that are to be carbonised. Since at the temperature of carbonisation these salts suffer volatilisation and then react with refractories, forming a glaze. This glaze coating reduces the effective life of a coke-oven or of a gas retort. This is precisely the reason why, ordinarily, the presence of an appreciable quantity of chlorine in a sample of coal is considered detrimental to the brick-work of coke-ovens and gas retorts. High chlorine in coal substance may not always be prejudicial to the stability of the refractories, as an appreciable percentage of it may be in organic combination. In the latter case, there may be either volatilisation or decomposition or both. Halogenated organic compounds have hardly any effect on refractories. If there be any liberation of hydrogen chloride gas or simple chlorine, due to decomposition, the refractories may be simply bleached (Washburn and Libman, *J. Amer. Ceram. Soc.*, 1920, 3, 635; Baskerville, *Science*, 1919, 50, 443). It thus transpires that a correct estimation of chlorine in organic combination has its profound usefulness. It is proposed to describe one such process in the present communication.

Some investigators have suggested that a part of the total chlorine might be in organic combination (Himus, "The Elements of Fuel Technology", 1947, p. 58). Literatures, however, reveal no experimental confirmation of this view. It is apparent from our findings that a part of the total chlorine is in organic combination, and, in some cases, its proportion is as high as 30--35% of the total.

The adoption of ter Meulen's method (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1928, 47, 698),

with slight modification, has been found to be very suitable for obtaining a true measure of the chlorine linked to organic compounds. The chlorides, however, are not affected by this treatment. This was verified by subjecting an artificial mixture of pure sodium chloride, sugar charcoal and 2:4:6-trichlorophenol to the modified process. The results (Table I) show that the organic compound only is affected. The process is very simple and entails a total period of one and half hour only. For a comparative study, the total chlorine content of each coal sample was also determined. It is evident that the difference between the total chlorine and that linked to organic compounds gives a measure of inorganic chlorine.

EXPERIMENTAL

The apparatus consisted of a silica tube, 55–60 cm. long and 1.5 cm. diam. This was mounted horizontally by two clamps; the vertical distance was so adjusted as to utilise fully the heating effect of three burners. One end of the tube was provided with a cork and a delivery tube with a view to connecting the same to a constant supply of pure hydrogen. The other end of the tube was kept open *via* a constricted tube. The boat containing the weighed sample was introduced into the tube near the end connected to the source of hydrogen and was placed at a distance of 8 cm. A nickel foil, rolled in the form of a spiral, was kept at a distance of 20 cm. from the same end. Another porcelain boat containing pure barium carbonate was placed just near the open end of the tube. At the outset, a steady stream of pure hydrogen, saturated with ammonia, was maintained through the tube. For this, the gas was bubbled successively through water, solutions of lead acetate and potassium hydroxide and liquor ammonia. The burner, immediately below the nickel catalyst, was started first. When the exterior surface of the tube was red hot, heating of the boat containing barium carbonate was made. The temperature of the boat with the powdered sample was raised gradually and the full temperature effect was allowed only after 15 minutes. Hydrogen combines with chlorine linked to organic compounds in presence of nickel. This then combines with ammonia forming ammonium chloride and is deposited on the inner walls between nickel catalyst and the open end. The least trace of unreacted hydrogen chloride is arrested by hot barium carbonate. The reaction requires a period of forty-five minutes. After the reaction was over, the tube was allowed to cool. This was then washed with water to dissolve the deposited ammonium chloride after withdrawing the boats and the spiral. Barium carbonate was also washed into the solution containing ammonium chloride. This was then rendered acidic by acetic acid and boiled to expel hydrocyanic acid, if any. Chloride was then estimated volumetrically in the usual way. Table I shows the results with 2:4:6-trichlorophenol and Table II shows results of experiments made with coals from different localities.

TABLE I

Expt. No.	Substance.	% Chlorine.	
		Found.	Calc.
1	2:4:6-Trichlorophenol	53.49	53.93
2	Do	53.56	53.93
3	Do (0.1440 g.) + NaCl (0.7917 g.)	54.10	53.93
4	Do (0.1509 g.) NaCl (1.023 g.)	54.09	53.93

TABLE II

Expt. No.	Particulars of coal sample.	Proximate analysis, excluding V. M.		% Organic chlorine.		% Total chlorine, (dry, ash-free basis).
		Ash.	Moisture.	As received.	Dry ash-free coal.	
1	Margherita Colliery, Assam.	4.83%	3.46%	0.089	0.097	0.395
				0.088	0.095	
				0.110	0.1247	
2	Balihari Colliery, 16 seam.	10.78	1.06	0.109	0.1236	0.495
				0.1045	0.127	
3	Charanpur Colliery.	13.43	4.30	0.1038	0.126	0.418
				0.036	0.042	
4	Bharat Colliery, 12 seam.	13.82	0.88	0.037	0.043	0.426
				0.027	0.032	
5	Do, 13 seam.	16.04	1.13	0.026	0.031	0.322
				0.456	0.647	
6	Dalmia Colliery.	28.81	0.76	0.459	0.651	...
				0.085	0.124	
7	Khas Junagora Colliery.	29.07	1.09	0.086	0.124	0.538
				0.0310	0.045	
8	Bright Kusunda Colliery, Dhansar.	30.60	0.53	0.0307	0.044	0.551
				0.066	0.082	
9	G/50/241.	17.06	2.28	0.066	0.082	0.340
				0.0493	0.068	
10	G/50/243.	27.22	1.01	0.0493	0.068	0.537
				0.101	0.126	
11	G/50/244.	19.19	1.08	0.102	0.127	0.350

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Received May 11, 1951